

SUPPORTING INFORMATION FOR

Insight into the role of guanidinium and cesium in triple cation lead halide perovskites

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Figure S1. Main reflection peaks of the X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements of mixed A-cation $\text{Gua}_x\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite films.

Figure S2. Main reflection peaks of the X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements of mixed A-cation $\text{Cs}_x\text{Gua}_y\text{MA}_{1-x-y}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite films.

Figure S3. SEM images of the mixed cation MAPbI_3 (A), $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.95}\text{PbI}_3$ (B), $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{Gua}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{PbI}_3$ (C) and $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{MA}_{0.85}\text{PbI}_3$ (D) perovskite films.

Table S1. Slopes obtained from the linear fit of the three regions for the mixed A-cation $\text{Cs}_x\text{Gua}_y\text{MA}_{1-x-y}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite films.

	Ohmic region	TFL region	Child region
MAPbI_3	0.92	6.42	1.64
$\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.95}\text{PbI}_3$	0.93	6.71	1.85
$\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{Gua}_{0.05}\text{MA}_{0.90}\text{PbI}_3$	1.00	4.42	1.60
$\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{Gua}_{0.10}\text{MA}_{0.85}\text{PbI}_3$	0.85	7.54	1.81

Figure S4. Stability test of the $\text{Cs}_x\text{Gua}_y\text{MA}_{1-x-y}\text{PbI}_3$ perovskite solar cells ($x = 0, 0.05, y = 0.05, 0.10$) at room temperature ($21\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) in ambient atmosphere.